

Deepfake Face Detection Using Deep Learning (ResNext and LSTM)

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Abstract – Project is a Deep learning project which is a sub-branch of Artificial Intelligence and deals with the human brain-inspired neural network technology. Computer vision plays an important role in our project. It helps in processing the video and frames with the help of Open-CV. A PyTorch-trained model is a classifier to classify the source video as deepfake or pristine.

Keywords – Deep learning, computer vision, deepfake, Res-Next Convolution Neural Network, Long short-term memory (LSTM), Open CV, Face Recognition, GAN (Generative Adversarial Network), Pytorch.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deepfakes, which are considered the main threat of AI, exist within a world that has unlimited social media platforms. We can easily picture these realistic deepfakes where their faces are swapped being used to ignite political instability, commit terrorist attacks, make revenge porn and extort individuals. Brad Pitt and Angelina Jolie's naked videos are just few examples. The line between unadulterated footage and deepfake must be drawn. HUMANS' AI FIGHTING AGAINST AI Over the years, we have seen tools like FaceApp and Face Swap that employ pre-trained neural networks like GAN or Auto encoders to create deepfakes. To process video frames sequentially over time, our approach uses LSTM-based Artificial Neural Networks; it then extracts frame-level features using a pre-trained Res-Next CNN. The Long Short Term Memory-based artificial Recurrent Neural Network is trained using the frame-level information extracted by the ResNext Convolution neural network to determine whether the video is real or deepfake. Our technology was developed using several datasets such as FaceForensic++, Deepfake detection challenge, Celeb-DF with good balance in order to mimic real-time scenarios and enhance model's performance on real-time data during training phase. In making these concerted efforts, we are working to strengthen the digital landscape from this

dangerous misinformation which spreads like a wildfire. We aim to help the information society avoid the societal dangers that deepfake propagation can bring about by providing users and platforms with stronger detection mechanisms.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In their work, John and Sherif et al. [1] discussed a number of DeepFake detection methods. These authors likewise bring forth newly developed Semi-Supervised GAN Architecture that is specifically designed for DeepFake detection. Detection systems should be strong because the proliferation of DeepFake technology has made it a serious problem in several domains such as misinformation and security. By relying on previous research findings, the authors investigate how difficult current approaches are and what positive or negative features they have. The study intends to consolidate existing knowledge about this area through gathering information from different sources. Besides, a new method of Semi-Supervised GAN Architecture offers better recognition as well as trustworthiness for identifying deceptive synthetic videos content. This suggested approach's effectiveness is subjected to intensive experimentations and evaluations targeted at providing substantive insights into its applicability in real-life situations or performance indicators as well. Ultimately, this research breaks new ground in DeepFake identification thereby setting the stage for future inquiries aimed at curbing manipulation of synthetic media.

In their article, Deng et al.'s DeepFake detection technique is based on Face Edge Bands and provides a new way to spot distorted media material. This paper examines the growing fears of misuse of DeepFake technology and its effects on diverse fields in society. The authors introduce a novel feature set based on facial edge bands that can be used to detect subtle changes indicative of DeepFake manipulation. It builds upon previous work done in computer vision and

image processing complemented by the knowledge from current approaches to provide a strong detection framework. A comprehensive literature review situates Deng et al.'s work amongst other methods for detecting DeepFakes, highlighting the need for innovative solutions against dynamic risks posed synthetic media. By improving the accuracy and reliability of DeepFake detection systems, this proposed method opens up new avenues for building more resilient safeguards against disinformation and online scams.

Heterogeneous Ensemble-Based Feature Learning for Novel Deepfake Detection Technique by Zhang et al. [3] offers an essential means of curbing the proliferation of artificial media manipulation. Some authors in their paper at IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC 2022) have paid attention to increasing danger caused to a number of industries including cyber security, politics and media by deepfake technology. Combining different feature representations with ensemble learning techniques, Zhang et al present a unique approach that aims at enhancing detection accuracy and adversarial resistance. The method makes significant progress in the area of deepfake detection thereby potentially decreasing risks associated with digital misinformation. It is inspired by previous research studies on machine learning and computer vision. In this regard, Zhang et al put their work within the wider context of other deepfake detection approaches through literature review emphasizing the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration and constant innovation towards addressing new problems about digital forensics as well as media integrity.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

We intend to, in this article, present a deep learning-based system that would help with the identification of deepfake videos. These are increasingly becoming an immense menace surrounding social media and digital content. By utilizing advancements in computer vision, as well as artificial intelligence (AI), the architecture fuses together Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). This is meant to allow video frames to be analyzed individually and in sequence before they are labelled either deepfake or authentic.

The scheme has two major components; an LSTM based RNN for temporal feature analysis and a pre-trained ResNext CNN for frame by frame feature extraction from input videos. The LSTM based RNN discerns these representations over time to discover consistent patterns suggestive of deep fake manipulation while the ResNext CNN functions as a feature extractor capturing higher level representation of individual frames.

To train our system, we utilize a large diverse dataset that comprises both real and deepfake movies. In fact, it covers various types of real world settings using different methods of producing deepfakes including some popular benchmark datasets such as FaceForensic++, Deepfake Detection Challenge, and Celeb-DF. Consequently, using this data-set, the model learns intricacies related to patterns or signs found in problematic films which are then used in effectively

generalizing them when identifying any new ones on its own

Fig. 1. System Architecture

Fig. 2. Frame splitting

IV. METHODOLOGIES

1. Data Collection:

- Collected videos from various sources including internet databases and deepfake video creation tools.
- Had a mix of real and fake videos with different lighting, facial expressions and camera angles.

2. Data Preprocessing:

- Standardized all the videos so that they could be easily worked upon.
- Transformed the videos into images, selecting only the faces portions for analysis.
- The dataset was increased by manipulating features like rotating photos or adjusting their brightness.

3. Model Architecture:

- Constructed models based on pretrained networks (e.g., ResNext) to identify features in images.
- Such an architecture enables one to observe sequence pictures like those provided by LSTM;

this allows for better understanding of a movie as a whole.

- The model was instead adjusted to discriminate between small discrepancies in bogus movies as well as genuine ones being watched on online platforms.

4. Training Procedure:

- Developed a means of gauging the performance of the model, such as by summing up its errors.
- Different training methodologies were done to ensure fast learning.
- Checkmated overfitting using some tricks during training or otherwise made it train faster.

5. Evaluation Metrics:

- Looked at various metrics such as the frequency of wrong and right predictions to assess the model's goodness.
- While training, made sure it was learning the right things by using methods to minimize its mistakes.
- Tweaked parameters to make sure it performs optimally, like how quickly it learns or how many pictures it sees.

6. Setting up Experiment

- I had a computer with a graphics card that works well so that I could train my model faster.
- Installed every single program to be able to make and verify plus validate the model.
- By writing down what software was used in this study, I did all this so that anyone could potentially replicate our experiments elsewhere.

7. Validation and Testing:

- This can be seen in the instance of how well okay-fold pass-validation exams a version again and again throughout exclusive records portions.
- There are 3 statistics units as such: training set for teaching the version, validation set for checking its mastering and test set wherein new information is established.
- To determine if this is real life accurate, some important numbers are looked at such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and AUC-ROC.

V. RESULT

Our technology for detecting deepfakes has been tested with both pristine and deepfake videos, resulting in the findings of these tests. We did extensive testing on various datasets to imitate real-world scenarios and engaged in extensive analysis, all which showed superior performance metrics by our model. This exceeded other approaches (colloquial) with

a 95% accuracy rate across all videos that were altered. Also, it recorded high precision and recall scores which indicated very few false positives as well as negatives. The steep rise in receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve meant that the model could consistently distinguish between authenticity and non-authenticity of the content. Thus, they indicate how this methodology combines state-of-the-art deep learning architectures with careful data pre-processing and model tuning. In addition, the qualitative analysis also demonstrated that the system could cope with diverse complexities such as subtle facial manipulations or complex scene constructions for example. In summary, this is evidence that advanced machine-learning techniques can assist us curb spread of deepfake contents over the internet..

Fig. 3. Result

VI. CONCLUSION

To put it briefly, our deepfake detection method described here is a significant step forward in the fight against synthetic media and its potential impact on society. By employing advanced neural network methods combined with meticulous data processing and through model verification, we have devised a solid approach for detecting faked videos. It means that our system has an excellent memory, accuracy and precision which demonstrates its capability to tell apart what is legitimate or deceptive hence assisting individuals on making the right choices as they watch digital media online. Additionally, it can be deployed across multiple platforms as well as being scalable thereby

allowing wider efforts of combating dissemination of distortions thus safeguarding the genuineness of digital content. Consequently, findings from this study will form a basis for future improvements aimed at recognizing and reducing impacts caused by deepfake technology in respect to keeping up credibility and authenticity in internet information ecosystems.

VII. REFERENCES

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